

Seasonal incidence of onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci* Lindeman) and its associated iris yellow spot virus (IYSV) infecting onion

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Abstract

Thrips tabaci, commonly known as onion thrips (Family: Thripidae; Order: Thysanoptera). *T. tabaci* is known to infest a variety of plants, with a preference for onion and other crops like garlic, leeks, and various vegetable crops. A study was conducted during Rabi 2022 in onion at Thondamathur, Tamil Nadu to know the influence of weather parameters on the *T. tabaci* population and iris yellow spot virus (IYSV) incidence. The results showed that the thrips population ranged from 1.32 to 14.2 thrips/onion plant and 20-46.67 per cent IYSV disease incidence. The thrips incidence starts from 42 DAT and attained maximum population of 14.2 thrips/onion plant, and suddenly decreased at 84 DAT due to rainfall. Both thrips and virus incidence correlated with maximum temperature positively at $r=0.47$ and $r=0.88$. Rainfall was negatively correlated with the thrips incidence at $r=-0.43$ in onion, where thrips population will attain zero.

Keywords: *Thrips tabaci*, iris yellow spot virus, weather parameters, tospovirus, onion.

Introduction

Tospoviruses transmitted by thrips are increasingly recognized as a notable constraint in achieving sustainable vegetable production and affecting economically crucial crops on a global scale. Presently, there have been global identifications of eighteen tospoviruses (Whitfield et al. 2005), with confirmation that eleven thrips species (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) serve as vectors in the transmission of these tospoviruses (Jones, 2005). Thrips feed by puncturing plant cells and extracting the contents. Their feeding can cause stippling, silvering, and distortion of leaves. In severe infestations, it can lead to reduced plant vigour and yield. Iris yellow spot virus (IYSV) can result in variable economic damage to onion crops. Research by (Poizzer et al. in 1999) revealed instances of up to 100% loss, while Kirtzman et al. 2001 reported 50-60% losses in onion bulb production in 2001. The

characteristic symptoms of IYSV infection manifest as distinctive diamond-shaped chlorotic or necrotic lesions. Additionally, there are indistinct circular to irregular lesions of varying sizes (du Toit et al. 2004). Over time, the diamond-shaped chlorotic lesions tend to coalesce, leading to the withering of leaves and flowering stalks. In severe cases, this can result in reduced size and yield of the onion crop (Gent et al. 2006). IYSV is exclusively transmitted by *T. tabaci*, making it the sole recognized vector of the virus on a global scale. While various thrips vector species are documented in diverse vegetable cropping systems across India, the transmission of IYSV is specifically attributed to *T. tabaci* in the country (Srinivasan et al., 2012). Understanding these seasonal dynamics is crucial for implementing effective management strategies to mitigate the impact on crops. Thrips populations often experience peaks during specific seasons (Kumawat and Kumawat, 2018). Monitoring and identifying these peak periods help farmers anticipate and prepare for potential infestations. Thrips are vectors for various plant viruses, including those causing significant damage to crops. Understanding when thrips are most active and likely to transmit viruses helps in implementing preventive measures to reduce disease incidence.

Materials and methods

Seasonal dynamics of *Thrips tabaci* and IYSV incidence

The study was conducted during 2022 in thondamathur (Coimbatore district, Tamil Nadu). Onion field from thondamathur (10.9947°N, 76.7998°E) was selected where disease incidence and mean thrips population count was recorded on weekly intervals starting from 10 days after bulb sowing to till harvest. Thrips mean population was counted by tapping the plants and counting the individual number of thrips present in each plant. Visual observation was made based on the symptom expression on the number of IYSV infected plants and the incidence was calculated by number of IYSV infected plants out of total number of plants observed and per cent disease incidence was worked out.

$$\text{Percent disease incidence} = \text{no of plants infected} / \text{no of plants observed} \times 100$$

Both thrips and IYSV incidences were correlated with weather parameters viz., maximum temperature (Tmax), minimum temperature (Tmin), relative humidity (RH), Wind speed (WS) and rainfall obtained from automatic weather station of Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore.

Statistical analysis:

Correlation and regression analysis of weather parameters with thrips and virus incidence were carried out with the help of R software 3.6.2.

Results

In Rabi-2022, results on the correlation analysis, the incidence of thrips population in onion started from 4th standard week which was 28 days after sowing (1.32 thrips/ onion shoots). Maximum population of thrips obtained from 8th standard week (11.05 thrips/ plant) and increased till 11th standard week (14.2 thrips/ onion shoots). At maximum the population of thrips (14.2 thrips/plant), the temperature was 35.31°C, RH was 77.57% in the morning and 29.86% in the evening and no precipitation (Table 1; Fig 1). When thrips population reached maximum, the incidence of IYSV started slightly (20%) at 7th standard week. After attaining maximum population, the population density of thrips decreased due to precipitation of about 0.14 and 1.17 mm, but the incidence of IYSV increased gradually and reached a maximum level (46.67 %) at 11th standard week and continued till 13th week. Maximum incidence of IYSV was noticed when temperature was increased to the maximum of 35.51°C and relative humidity ranged from 77.57% in the morning and 29.86% in the evening. Occurrence of precipitation was recorded as 0.14mm and 1.17 mm at 12th and 13th standard week (Table 1).

The correlation analysis between IYSV incidence and weather parameters revealed that there was significant correlation observed between them (Fig 1). Thrips population and virus incidence are positively correlated with maximum temperature.

Table 1. Seasonal dynamics of *T. tabaci* and IYSV in onion (Rabi- 2022)

SMW	Max. Temp (°C) (X1)	Min. Temp (°C) (X2)	RH mng. (%) (X3)	RH evg. (%) (X4)	Rainfall (mm) (X5)	Wind speed (km/h) (X6)	Thrips incidence (mean population) (X7)	IYSV incidence (%) (X8)
1	28.21	21	84.43	56.57	2.37	6.3	0	0
2	30.43	21.29	84.57	50	0	4	0	0
3	30.79	20.64	85.14	46.14	0	5.5	0	0
4	31.57	19	85.14	42.86	0	4.4	1.32	0
5	31.11	21.23	84.43	47.14	0	5.7	3.37	0
6	32.19	20.73	85	40.43	0	4.6	7.9	0
7	31.21	21.04	82.86	45.14	0	5.1	7.5	20
8	32.64	22.29	83.29	38.86	0	5.6	11.05	26.67
9	32.84	19.43	77.86	28	0	6	11.58	33.33
10	33.4	21.26	76.86	41.43	0	5.9	13.6	33.33
11	35.31	21.03	77.57	29.86	0	4.7	14.2	46.67
12	34.96	23.39	85	44.43	0.14	4.3	2.4	46.67
13	35.14	24.07	87.29	44.71	1.17	4	0	46.67

Figure 1. Weather correlation with of *T. tabaci* and IYSV in onion (Rabi- 2022)

Multiple linear regression analysis between weather parameters and occurrence of thrips population and IYSV incidence was represented in Table 2. The statistical analysis showed that the rainfall was negatively correlated with thrips incidence, followed by relative humidity (morning and evening) were also negatively correlated (Table 2). The percent incidence of IYSV was ranged from 20 to 46.67 per cent. According to linear regression equation, the incidence of *T. tabaci* ($R^2 = 0.85$) and IYSV ($R^2 = 0.92$) was influenced by weather parameters up to 85.9 and 92.0 percent respectively (Table 2).

Table 2. Linear Regression Equation for incidence of *T. tabaci* and IYSV with weather parameters in onion (Rabi- 2022)

Particulars	Regression equation	R ² value
No. of thrips/plant	$Y = 96.15 - 0.76X_1 + 1.48X_2 - 0.99X_3 - 0.41X_4 - 1.18X_5 + 0.64X_6$	0.85
IYSV incidence	$Y = -81.14 + 5.46X_1 + 5.56X_2 - 2.09X_3 - 0.47X_4 + 6.83X_5 - 0.27X_6$	0.92

Y= thrips incidence/IYSV incidence; X1= Max. Temp (°C), Min. Temp (°C), X3= RH mng. (%), X4= RH evg. (%), X5= Rainfall (mm), X6= Wind speed (km/h), X7= Thrips incidence (mean population), X8= IYSV incidence (%).

Discussion

At initial stage of crop, population of *T. tabaci* in onion was nil and started after 42 days after transplant of bulbs, whereas the IYSV disease incidence started after thrips incidence and where in non-infected plant would have attracted viruliferous thrips as evidenced from earlier works on aphid-PLRV-potato (Rajabaskar et al., 2014), WBNV (Arunkumar et al., 2020; Arunkumar et al., 2022), IYSV (Arunkumar et al., 2023) and whitefly–MYMV-Mungbean pathosystems (Ranjithkumar et al., 2018). The vector preference was influenced by virus in order to spread the disease and also the preference varies with stage of inoculation (Rajabaskar et al., 2013). This might be due to increased population at earlier stage. The increase in temperature lead to increased number of thrips per plant and incidence of IYSV which confirms that the earlier reports, which showed that major factors affecting population dynamics of thrips are temperature and rainfall (Morsello et al., 2014). Both factors influence the multiplication rate of thrips population with negative correlation (Momol et al., 2004) which were observed in the present study. Incidence of thrips was higher during dry weather condition (Mandal and Mondal, 2023). In the present investigation, due to rainfall there is a sudden decrease in the thrips population, but the incidence of virus was remain unchanged without increase or decrease as the infected onion plants remain in the field after infestation.

Conclusion

The seasonal incidence of thrips plays a pivotal role in shaping pest management strategies in agriculture. Thrips activity tends to vary throughout the year based on environmental conditions, temperature, and crop phenology. Understanding the seasonal dynamics of thrips can be instrumental in developing targeted and effective control measures.

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